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Fingerprint Pattern Examination of Right Hand Thumb In Relation to Blood Groups

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Abstract

Fingerprint evidence is undoubtedly the most reliable and acceptable evidence till date in the court of law. Due to the immense potential of fingerprints as an effective method of identification an attempt has been made in the present work to analyze their correlation with fingerprint pattern of right hand thumb and blood group of an individual. This prospective study was conducted in the School of Forensic Science, SHIATS in form of dissertation work, where 100 fingerprint sample of right hand thumb (81 male & 19 female) belonging to the age group 18- 45 were analysed. Results shown that the frequency distribution of Loop ridges pattern was highest (76.92%) in AB blood and (71.79%) in 'O' blood group. In blood group ABO pattern was (57.14%). Similarly the Whorls pattern of ridges was highest in blood group A and B with the frequency distribution of fingerprints pattern 42.86% and 39.28%, respectively. In blood group O the whorls pattern was 28.95%, while lowest were in AB blood group i.e. (23.08%). The arches patterns of ridges were least with 3.84% in blood group B. Therefore it may be concluded that there is a close association between distribution of fingerprint patterns and blood groups thus prediction of blood group of a person may be possible based on his/her fingerprint pattern.

Keywords: - Fingerprint, Blood group, Ridge Pattern, Identification, thumb imprint

Introduction

During early embryonic development (four to five weeks) there is swelling of (mesenchymal) tissue on areas of the sole, palm and digits. These areas are known as volar pads. The pads stop growing at about 10 weeks of development but the hand continues to grow. The volar pads are then absorbed back into the hand and as the pads shrink the skin folds to produce the ridges of fingerprints. The first ridge begins to appear at around 10 weeks.

Based on the pattern of pad absorption and timing, various combinations of fingerprint can occur:

- If ridges appear when the volar pads are quite pronounced, the ridge pattern is a whorl ?
- If ridges appear when the volar pads are less pronounced, the ridge pattern is a loop ?
- If ridges appear when the volar pads are nearly absorbed, the ridge pattern is an arch ?

Timing and absorption during development is genetically influenced; this is why identical twins have similar ridge patterns. However, within the general friction ridge pattern there are many small variations known as minutiae. The development of minutiae is a result of the environment and external stresses and pressures such as growth. So while identical twins may have very close similarities in their fingerprints, they do not have identical fingerprints as they are subject to different stresses and pressures while they are in the womb.

There are other elements than ridges that make up a fingerprint. These are sweat pores which can be located along the ridges. Sweat pores are spaced almost evenly along the ridges and they are responsible for secretions, which can sometimes leave fingerprints at the scene of a crime.

Fingerprints are the marks left behind when someone touches an object with their finger.

There are three types of fingerprints that can be left behind.

- An impression left in something soft (such as butter, putty, soap or wet paint)
- A print left by a finger that is covered in something that is left behind such as dirt, blood, paint or ink.

- An invisible deposit left by secretions from the skin. Everyone's fingers have small amounts of oil and perspiration which come out of microscopic pores on the tiny ridges of the fingerprints. These secretions also come out of different parts of the body too.

There are three basic principles about why forensics scientists use fingerprints as evidence:

1. After almost a century of fingerprint existence, no two fingers have ever been found to possess identical ridge characteristics.
2. A fingerprint remains unchanged during a person's lifetime. (Unless they are involved in an accident which affects their hands.)
3. Fingerprints have ridge characteristics that allow for efficient classification and examination.

A reliable personal identification is critical in the subject of forensics as is faced with many situations like civil, criminal, commercial and latest in financial transaction frauds, where the question of identification becomes a matter of paramount importance. Although human beings have been using fingerprints as a means of identification for a long time but in

this study an effort has been made to take one step further to “study a relationship between fingerprint pattern and ABO Rh blood group”, so that one can get an idea about the expected blood group from the study of fingerprint pattern and vice versa.

The pattern of fingerprint ridges and pores is unique in each person; no two people have the exact same pattern of ridges. It seems that the general pattern of friction ridges may be genetic; however the specific pattern or fine detail is unique. Even for identical twins this is true: they may have similar general patterns but the fine details or ‘minutiae’ (my-new-shay) are different. Fingerprints are often used to identify or eliminate suspects from a crime. These days, with security being so important, the field of biometrics (the process by which distinguishing human anatomy is used for identification and verification of a person) is becoming increasingly important.

The evidence available through blood typing is not as convincing as genetic fingerprinting, but it can readily prove innocence or increase the probability of a defendant being guilty. All humans belong to one of four blood groups—A, B, AB, or O. These blood groups are based on genetically determined antigens (A and/or B) that may be attached to the red blood cells. These

antigens are either present or absent in blood. By adding specific antibodies (anti-A or anti-B) the presence or absence of the A and B antigens can be determined. If the blood cells carry the A antigen, they will clump together in the presence of the anti-A antibody. Similarly, red blood cells carrying the B antigen will clump when the anti-B antibody is added. Type A blood contains the A antigen; type B blood carries the B antigen; type AB blood carries both antigens; and type O blood, the most common, carries neither antigen. To determine the blood type of a blood sample, antibodies of each type are added to separate samples of the blood.

Material and Methods

100 samples of right hand thumb impression along with their blood groups (male and female) were collected from age group 18-45. Each subject was asked to wash his hands thoroughly with soap and water and dried them using a towel. The individual being fingerprinted were asked to stand in front of and at a forearm's length stretched from the fingerprinting paper. He was then asked to press his/her right hand thumb on the stamp pad and then to the paper gently to transfer the fingerprint impression by following steps (a) a plain of print was taken by applying ink to the tip of right hand thumb

and place in the thumb directly on paper with a gentle pressure. (b) The rolled fingerprint was taken by rolling the thumb on paper from outward to inward in such a way as to obtain an impression of whole tip. In this way, the plain fingerprints of right hand thumb were taken separately on the respective blocks on the same sheet of paper. Care was taken to avoid sliding of right hand thumb to prevent smudging of the print. After the fingerprints were acquired, details such as name, sex and blood group were noted. The details of their blood group were noted from their genuine document. Each subject was assigned a serial number. The fingerprint patterns (loops, whorl and

arches) were studied with the help of a magnifying lens and were identified as: Loops, Whorls and Arches based on the appearance of ridge lines according to Henry's system of classification. The distribution of dermatoglyphic fingerprint patterns of right hand thumb of individuals and its relationship with their different ABO and Rh blood groups were evaluated and analyzed.

Result & Discussion

All the samples of right hand thumb fingerprints were collected and analyzed statistically with their blood groups and tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1- Distribution of various fingerprints pattern with Blood groups. (N =100)

Fingerprints Types	Blood gr. A	Blood gr. B	Blood gr. O	Blood gr. AB	Total Finger type
Loops	12 (57.14%)	16 (57.14%)	27 (71.05%)	10 (76.92%)	65
Whorls	9(42.86%)	11 (39.28%)	11 (28.95%)	3 (23.08%)	34
Arches	0	1 (3.57%)	0	0	1
Total	21	28	38	13	100

Data given in the Table 1 shows that frequency and percentage wise distribution of various fingerprint patterns along with their ABO blood groups. It was observed that percentage of Loops were highest in AB blood group having 76.92% and O blood group with 71.05%, There was common

pattern in A and B blood groups with 57.14%. Also, percentage of Whorls in A blood group was highest with 42.86% as compared to lowest in AB blood group of 23.08%. In blood group B and O the distribution of whorls pattern were 39.28% and 28.95% respectively. Similarly,

percentage of Arch was least in B blood group having only 3.84%.

Percentage distribution of Fingerprint pattern in ABO blood group

$$\text{Pattern \%} = \frac{\text{No.of pattern types}}{\text{Total no.of blood group}} \times 100$$

This study revealed that blood group AB and O had highest incidence of loops with 76.92% and 71.05% respectively, followed by whorls having 23.08% and 28.95% respectively. Similarly in blood group A and B the loops pattern were common with 57.14% in both cases. The revealed that the whorls pattern were highest in blood group A and B with 42.86% and 39.82% respectively, while in blood group O and AB the frequency distribution of whorls were 28.95% and 23.08% respectively. Finally the frequency distribution of arch was 3.57% in blood group B.

The result showed the general distribution pattern of the right hand thumb fingerprint was of the same order in individuals with A, B, AB and O blood groups i.e. high frequency of loops, moderate of whorls and low of arches. This finding is in accordance with the study conducted by Bharadwaj *et al.* (2004). This study also shows that loops pattern were highest in blood group AB and O, and common in blood group A and B in both cases. Similarly whorls were highest in A and B blood group than AB and O blood group, this finding was supported to the

study conducted by Noor *et al.* (2010) and Rastogi *et al.* (2010). so a possible association has also been found between distributions of Fingerprint pattern and blood groups. However male and female subjects had no difference in pattern & blood groups.

Conclusion

The dissertation work was conducted in the School of Forensic Science on the 100 sample of fingerprint of right hand thumb and blood group among them 81 male and 19 female. The dissertation work was based on fingerprint pattern examination of right hand thumb in relation to blood group. Study concluded that there is a strong correlation between blood groups and fingerprint pattern. From the study, it was concluded that the frequency distribution loops pattern were highest in blood group AB having 76.92 %, O 71.05% and B 57.14%. Similarly, the study also concluded that the distribution of whorls were highest in blood group A with 42.86% distribution, than in blood group B with 39.28% distribution and for blood group AB it was

found 23.08% and arches were least in blood group B with merely 3.57% distribution.

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